

EUROPEAN MIDDLEWARE INITIATIVE

MYPROXY YAIM – ADMINISTRATOR GUIDE

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1 MYPROXY CONFIGURATION BY YAIM

1.1 NAME

yaim - YAIM (YAIM Aint an Installation Manager) is, as the name suggests, a way of configuring Grid Services. The aim of YAIM is to provide a simple installation and configuration method that can be used to set up a simple Grid Site but can be easily adapted and extended to meet the need of larger sites. The yaim-myproxy module is configuring the MyProxy server.

1.2 DESCRIPTION

The yaim-myproxy module allows you to configure the MyProxy server.

1.3 CONFIGURATION VARIABLES

This is the list of variables needed to set up in order to configure the MyProxy server.

For more details, please check:

https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/LCG/PX_configuration_variables

Mandatory Variables:

Site admins must ensure these variables are properly defined according to the features of the site
site-info.def variables: These variables are defined in `/opt/glite/yaim/examples/site-info.def`.

INSTALL_ROOT : Installation root - change if using the re-locatable distribution.

SITE_NAME : The GUIS of the site where the MyProxy server belongs to.

GLOBUS_TCP_PORT_RANGE: Port range for Globus IO. It should be specified as "num1,num2". YAIM automatically handles the syntax of this variable depending on the version of VDT. If it's VDT 1.6 it leaves "num1,num2". If it's a version < VDT 1.6 it changes to "num1 num2".

node specific variables: These variables are defined in `/opt/glite/yaim/examples/services/glite-px`.

GRID_TRUSTED_BROKERS : List of the DNs of the Resource Brokers host certificates which are trusted by the Proxy node. (ex: `/O=Grid/O=CERN/OU=cern.ch/CN=host/testbed013.cern.ch`). Now deprecated, use **GRID_DEFAULT_RENEWERS** instead.

GRID_AUTHORIZED_RENEWERS : List of authorized_renewrs.

GRID_DEFAULT_RENEWERS : List of default_renewers

GRID_AUTHORIZED_RETRIEVERS : List of authorized_retrievers.

GRID_DEFAULT_RETRIEVERS : List of default_retrievers.

GRID_AUTHORIZED_KEY_RETRIEVERS : List of authorized_key_retrievers.

GRID_DEFAULT_KEY_RETRIEVERS : List default_key_retrievers.

GRID_TRUSTED_RETRIEVERS : List of trusted_retrievers.

GRID_DEFAULT_TRUSTED_RETRIEVERS : List of default_trusted_retrievers.

GRID_ALLOW_SELF_AUTHORIZATION : Enable refreshing or renewing proxy by itself. Enabling this is not recommended for security reasons - the compromised proxy could be renewed indefinitely.

MYPROXY_DISABLE_USAGE_STATS : Disable Usage Metrics reporting. The myproxy server may be blocked when target server is inaccessible, thus you may want to disable it.

1.4 EXAMPLES

How to configure the Myproxy node.

```
cat << EOF > /root/site-info.def
SITE_NAME=emitb
PX_HOST=`hostname -f`
GRID_AUTHORIZED_RETRIEVERS="$\backslash$*"
GRID_AUTHORIZED_RENEWERS="
    '/DC=org/DC=terena/DC=tcs/C=CZ/O=Masaryk University/CN=emitb2.ics.muni.cz'
    '/DC=ch/DC=cern/OU=computers/CN=cvitbrnagios.cern.ch'
    '/DC=ch/DC=cern/OU=computers/CN=lxbra2302.cern.ch'
"
GRID_TRUSTED_RETRIEVERS="
    '/DC=ch/DC=cern/OU=computers/CN=cvitbrnagios.cern.ch'
"
EOF
/opt/glite/yaim/bin/yaim -c -s /root/site-info.def -n glite-PX
```

To debug the configuration process:

```
/opt/glite/yaim/bin/yaim -c -s /root/site-info.def -n glite-PX -d 6
```

1.5 DOCUMENTATION

You can find useful information on these web pages:

Entry point for YAIM documentation:

<https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/EGEE/YAIM>

The Generic Installation and Configuration guides as well as the YAIM guides:

<https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/LCG/LcgDocs>

Useful links:

<http://lcg.web.cern.ch/LCG/Sites/the-LCG-directory.html>

1.6 AUTHORS

YAIM is a collaborative project where different modules are developed and maintained by different groups. Here are some of the present contributors:

Maria Allandes Pradillo, Gergely Debreczeni, Laurence Field, Di Qing, Andreas Unterkircher, Oliver Keeble, Steve Traylen, Owen Syngé, Gavin Mccance , Maarten Litmaath, and we are happy to receive patches from everybody !

1.7 CONTACT

To contact YAIM people use the yaim-contact@cern.ch email address.

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- Name
- Description
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2 YAIM-LESS MYPROXY DEPLOYMENT PROCEDURE – SCIENTIFIC LINUX

```
#!/bin/sh
# The primary purpose of this script is to document the procedure that may
# be followed in case MyProxy server cannot be configured by YAIM

DN='openssl x509 -in /etc/grid-security/hostcert.pem -noout -subject |sed 's
    /subject= //''
echo "$DN"
#cp -p /etc/myproxy-server.config /tmp
cat >> /etc/myproxy-server.config <<EOF

# local configuration for 'uname -n'
authorized_renewers "$DN"
authorized_retrievers "*"
EOF

cp -pv /etc/grid-security/host*.pem /etc/grid-security/myproxy
chown -v myproxy:myproxy /etc/grid-security/myproxy/host*.pem

/etc/init.d/myproxy-server restart

chkconfig myproxy-server on

#
# setup BDII resource (optional)
#
# required packages: bdii glite-info-provider-service sudo redhat-lsb
#

INFO_SERVICE_CONFIG='/etc/glite/info/service'
SITE_NAME='sitename'

cp ${INFO_SERVICE_CONFIG}/glite-info-service-myproxy.conf.template ${
    INFO_SERVICE_CONFIG}/glite-info-service-myproxy.conf
cp ${INFO_SERVICE_CONFIG}/glite-info-glue2-myproxy.conf.template ${
    INFO_SERVICE_CONFIG}/glite-info-glue2-myproxy.conf
cat <<EOF >/var/lib/bdii/gip/provider/glite-info-provider-service-myproxy-
wrapper
/usr/bin/glite-info-service ${INFO_SERVICE_CONFIG}/glite-info-service-
myproxy.conf $SITE_NAME
/usr/bin/glite-info-glue2-simple ${INFO_SERVICE_CONFIG}/glite-info-glue2-
myproxy.conf $SITE_NAME
EOF
chmod +x /var/lib/bdii/gip/provider/glite-info-provider-service-myproxy-
wrapper

# newer slapd with rwm backend required for SL5
```

```
[ -x /usr/sbin/slapd2.4 ] && echo "SLAPD=/usr/sbin/slapd2.4" >> /etc/  
sysconfig/bdii
```

```
chkconfig bdii on  
/etc/init.d/bdii restart
```

3 YAIM-LESS MYPROXY DEPLOYMENT PROCEDURE – DEBIAN

```
#!/bin/sh
# The primary purpose of this script is to document the procedure that may
# be followed in case MyProxy server cannot be configured by YAIM

DN='openssl x509 -in /etc/grid-security/hostcert.pem -noout -subject |sed 's
    /subject= //''
echo "$DN"
#cp -p /etc/myproxy-server.config /tmp
cat >> /etc/myproxy-server.config <<EOF

# local configuration for 'uname -n'
authorized_renewers "$DN"
authorized_retrievers "*"
EOF

cp -pv /etc/grid-security/host*.pem /etc/grid-security/myproxy
chown -v myproxy:myproxy /etc/grid-security/myproxy/host*.pem

/etc/init.d/myproxy-server restart

#cp -p /etc/init.d/myproxy-server /tmp/
sed -i /etc/init.d/myproxy-server -e 's/\(# Default-Start:\) .*/\1      2 3 4
    5/'
sed -i /etc/init.d/myproxy-server -e 's/\(# Default-Stop:\) .*/\1      0 1
    6/'
update-rc.d myproxy-server defaults

#
# setup BDII resource (optional)
#
# required packages: bdii glite-info-provider-service sudo lsb-release
#

INFO_SERVICE_CONFIG='/etc/glite/info/service'
SITE_NAME='sitename'

cp ${INFO_SERVICE_CONFIG}/glite-info-service-myproxy.conf.template ${
    INFO_SERVICE_CONFIG}/glite-info-service-myproxy.conf
cp ${INFO_SERVICE_CONFIG}/glite-info-glue2-myproxy.conf.template ${
    INFO_SERVICE_CONFIG}/glite-info-glue2-myproxy.conf
cat <<EOF >/var/lib/bdii/gip/provider/glite-info-provider-service-myproxy-
wrapper
/usr/bin/glite-info-service ${INFO_SERVICE_CONFIG}/glite-info-service-
myproxy.conf $SITE_NAME
/usr/bin/glite-info-glue2-simple ${INFO_SERVICE_CONFIG}/glite-info-glue2-
```

```
myproxy.conf $SITE_NAME
EOF
chmod +x /var/lib/bdii/gip/provider/glite-info-provider-service-myproxy-
wrapper

BDII_PASSWD='dd if=/dev/random bs=1 count=10 2>/dev/null | base64'
cat << EOF > /etc/default/bdii
RUN=yes
SLAPD_CONF=
SLAPD=
BDII_RAM_DISK=
EOF
sed -i "s#.*rootpw.*#rootpw\t${BDII_PASSWD}#" /etc/bdii/bdii-slapd.conf

/etc/init.d/bdii restart
```